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Research Article

**COMPLIANCE AND ADHERENCE TO TREATMENT IN
HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS
OF LAHORE**¹Azhar Hussain, ²Dr. Muhammad Hanif Sultan, ²Dr. Muhammad Adil Khan,¹Student of 2nd year MBBS, Ameer Ud Din Medical College, PGMI, Lahore²House Officers, Lahore General Hospital, Lahore**Abstract:****Objective:** To determine that factors that affect compliance and adherence to medications undergoing hypertensive treatment in hypertensive patients.**Design:** Descriptive type of cross sectional**Place and duration of study:** It took 8 months starting from 2 August 2017 to 29 March 2018 in Lahore General Hospital, Mayo Hospital Lahore and DHQ Layyah**Subjects and Methods:** Purposive sample 165 ward patients with questionnaire on sociodemographic and compliance and adherence were filled.**Results and Conclusion:** Major causes of non-adherent nature were expensive medications, lack of symptoms, lack of money, forgetfulness, lack of awareness due to poor educational status and irregularity in drugs consumptions due to non-serious attitude to the potential harms of the disease.**Keywords:** Compliance, adherence, medications, forgetfulness**Corresponding Author:****Azhar Hussain,**Student of 2nd year MBBS,

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INTRODUCTION:

American Heart Association (AHA) and American College of Cardiology (ACC) defined the new lower readings of hypertension. They considered blood pressure in normal range if Systolic blood pressure/Diastolic blood pressure should be lower than 120/80 mm Hg; for increased blood pressure, SBP between 120-129 mmHg and DBP lower than 80 mmHg; for hypertension stage-1, SBP should be less than 130-139 mmHg with DBP between 80-89 mmHg; for hypertension stage-2, systolic BP equal to or above 140 mmHg with diastolic BP as 90 mm Hg [1]. WHO exposed in its report in Geneva, 2013 that elevated blood pressure was found to be a major culprit in causing 7.5 million deaths throughout the world, so rightly considered as a "Silent Killer" [2,3]. Medication adherence is the other name of extent to which the behavior of a patient of medication-taking coincides with recommendations from a health care provider. [4] It is a major and important factor for controlling disease. Our research focuses on asking essential questions to develop understanding by the patients about their own condition and health beliefs. So, in improving their behavior to medication. A cluster randomized controlled trial documented that reduction in blood pressure due to higher compliance and better adherence to lifestyle recommendations. [5]

A recent meta-analysis of 94 studies in Netherland documented in that concerns about the side effects of drugs, loss of sexual activities performance, or better effects of traditional remedies must be cleared by health care provider in order to increase adherence to antihypertensive medication. [6]

In a Malaysian study, carried out in a primary care in the district of Melaka Tengah, it was found that 56% of the 464 sampled patients taking antihypertensives medications. [7] In another study 51.3% of patients interviewed had poor adherence to prescribed hypertensive medications. [8]

A cohort study among hypertensive patients showed that factors compromising the rates of adherence included duration of hypertension. Much higher rates and better adherence in hypertensive patients had been reported with shorter and precise duration of drugs taking. Adherence was also affected by the use of some advanced and new agents including angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors, calcium antagonists, and thiazide diuretics. [9]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted from 2 August 2017 to 29 March 2018 in Lahore General Hospital, Mayo

Hospital Lahore and DHQ Layyah. This was a Cross sectional survey. Sample was collected by non-probability way.

There were 165 patients of either sex included in this study of both gender having age above 18 years to medical ward.

A standardized questionnaire on sociodemographic status including name, gender, marital status, age, education, medications, blood pressure charting, supplements, regularity, forgetfulness and lack of money and symptoms.

Systolic and Diastolic blood pressure was measured by the research participants. Information was collected, and data was entered in SPSS version 20. It is a descriptive study so there is no need to apply any test. Frequencies and percentages are calculated for qualitative variables gender, marital status, education, medications, BP charting, supplements, regularity, forgetfulness and lack of money and symptoms.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

Hypertensive patients of both gender taking oral medication for 3 months having age 18 years or above.

Exclusion criteria:

All the patients of hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis dysfunction or other pituitary or adrenal tumors were excluded from study.

RESULTS:

A total of 165 ward patients were included in this study of Compliance and adherence to treatment in hypertensive patients. Age ranges from 18 to 80 years.

Among 165 patients, male was 89{53.9%} and female 76{46.1%}. 138{83.6%} married 27{16.4%} unmarried. Patient whom used to do BP charting 13{7.9%} and those without BP charting 152{92.1%} (**Pie chart 1**). And this result is congruent to an American nursing practitioners study. [10] Those who have taken medication 37{22.4%} and those who have not taken medication 128{77.6%} (**Pie chart 2**). Those who were regular in their medication 20{12.1%} and those who were not regular 145{87.9%} (**Pie chart 3**). These above-mentioned results are correspondent to the Malaysian study. [11] Those who forgot to take the medication 78{47.3%} and those who did not forget 87{52.7%} (**Pie chart 4**). Lack of money 34{20.6%} and who did not have lack of money 131{79.4%} (**Pie chart**

5).Lack of symptoms were in 32{19.4%} and with symptoms 133{80.6%} (**Pie chart 6**) and these results matched to a Chinese study. [12]. Most commonly prescribed classes of antihypertensive drugs included Loop Diuretics, Beta Blockers, ACE (Angiotensin Converting Enzyme) Inhibitors,

Thiazide Diuretics, Calcium Channel Blockers and Angiotensin-II Receptors Blockers by the healthcare staff of Lahore General Hospital, Mayo Hospital Lahore and DHQ Layyah. (**Table 1**)

(Table 1). Table Showing Count and Row N % of Different Variables:

Gender	Male	Count	89
		Row N %	53.9%
	Female	Count	76
		Row N %	46.1%
Education	No Formal Education	Count	110
		Row N %	66.7%
	1-8 Years	Count	22
		Row N %	13.3%
9+ Years	Count	33	
	Row N %	20.0%	
Marital Status	Married	Count	138
		Row N %	83.6%
	Unmarried	Count	27
		Row N %	16.4%
Age	18-39 Years	Count	51
		Row N %	30.9%
	40-59 Years	Count	59
		Row N %	35.8%
60+ Years	Count	55	
	Row N %	33.3%	
Medication Information	No Medication	Count	0
		Row N %	0.0%
	Loop Diuretics	Count	31
		Row N %	18.8%
	Beta Blockers	Count	28
		Row N %	17.0%
	ACE Inhibitors	Count	8
		Row N %	4.8%
	Thiazide Diuretics	Count	44
		Row N %	26.7%
Calcium Channel Blockers	Count	11	
	Row N %	6.7%	
Angiotensin-II Receptors Blockers	Count	43	
	Row N %	26.1%	
B.P Charting	Yes	Count	13
		Row N %	7.9%
	No	Count	152
		Row N %	92.1%
Non-Prescription Medication/Supplements	Yes	Count	37
		Row N %	22.4%
	No	Count	128
		Row N %	77.6%
Regularity	Yes	Count	20
		Row N %	12.1%
	No	Count	145

Forgetfulness	Yes	Row N %	87.9%
		Count	78
	No	Row N %	47.3%
		Count	87
Lack of Money	Yes	Row N %	20.6%
		Count	34
	No	Row N %	79.4%
		Count	131
Lack of Symptoms	Yes	Row N %	19.4%
		Count	32
	No	Row N %	80.6%
		Count	133

Pie chart 1: Frequencies and number of patients showing their habit of BP Charting

Pie chart 2: Frequencies and number of patients showing their regularity.

Pie chart 3: Frequencies and number of patients showing the effect of forgetfulness.**DISCUSSION:**

Uncontrolled blood pressure in chronic hypertensive patients can cause serious life-threatening results and consequences like higher incidence of mortality and morbidity. It also causes a great economic burden to the health care sector and national health budget. Compliance and adherence to antihypertensive prescribed drugs are important factor that can affect

blood pressure control drastically. A much higher level of improvement occurs in blood pressure control with a small improvement in adherence. The awareness and intervention programs should be planned for the betterment of non-adherent nature and behavior of the patients. In this current study, we made some efforts to identify the reasons for non adherence and then, suggesting few steps to be taken

to improve it, through a better connection and communication between health care staff and hypertensive patients.

In our study, major cause of non-compliance among the patients was forgetfulness nature of patients. The cost of medication is another factor to compromise the adherence and thus, for efforts to control BP. The poor patients were less likely to adhere to the prescribed expensive medications due to their unaffordability to purchase drugs regularly to the families with poor sociodemographic status with no permanent sources of income and our study results are in correspondence to the Malaysian study [11].

Other causes of compromised compliance to treatment were found to be the irregularity in consumption of medication, lack of symptoms and use of other non-prescribed drugs. Similarly, BP Charting can be beneficial in blood pressure control in helping them to be compliant, adherent and regular in consumptions of medications as recommended by the American Heart Association (AHA) [12].

Our study also revealed that most of the physicians do prescribe the medications by the pharmaceutical trademark name rather than their generic and class name. Most commonly prescribed antihypertensive drugs were by their classic and generic names included Loop Diuretics, Beta Blockers, Thiazide Diuretics, Calcium Channel Blockers, Angiotensin-II Receptors Blockers, and ACE (Angiotensin Converting Enzyme) Inhibitors by the healthcare staff of Lahore General Hospital, Mayo Hospital Lahore and DHQ Layyah.

CONCLUSION:

Major causes of non-adherent nature were expensive medications, lack of symptoms, lack of money, forgetfulness, lack of awareness due to poor educational status and irregularity in drugs consumptions due to non-serious attitude to the potential harms of the disease. Only 7.88% used to perform BP Charting to manage their blood pressure.

SUGGESTIONS:

Large number of steps must be taken by health care professionals through counseling sessions to help patients organize their medication consumption. This could be achieved by planning for medication intake to correspond with certain activities, such as five prayers a day particularly asking them to take medication after offering Fajar and Isha prayer, with eating meals, or by setting alarms to go off at medicine-taking time during the initial stages of their therapy.

LIMITATIONS

First, the study design was way simple infer a fully reliable correlation that was descriptive type of cross-sectional study.

Second, as we only recruited ward patients aged above 18 years old, some selection bias might confound the results.

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REFERENCES:

1. Lower Definition of Hypertension; New ACC/AHA High Blood Pressure Guidelines, Nov 13, 2017. Available at: <http://www.acc.org/latest-in-cardiology/articles/2017/11/08/11/47/mon-5pm-bp-guideline-aha-2017>. Accessed at 29th April, 2018.
2. World Health Organization. A global brief on hypertension. Silent killer, global public health crisis. Geneva 2013. Available from: http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/79059/1/WHO_DCO_WH_D_2013.2_eng.pdf?ua=. Accessed at 29th April, 2018.
3. Savva SC, Kourides YA, Hadjigeorgioua C, Tornaritis MJ. Overweight and obesity prevalence and trends in children and adolescents in Cyprus 2000-2010. *Obesity Res Clin Pract* 2013; ORCP-348, article in press.
4. Sabaté E. Adherence to long-term therapies: evidence for action. World Health Organization; [Updated 2003; cited May 2012]. Available from: <http://apps.who.int/medicinedocs/en/d/Js4883e/6.1.3.html>. Accessed at 29th April, 2018.
5. Beune EJ, Moll van Charante EP, Beem L, Mohrs J, Agyemang CO, Ogedegbe G, et

- al. Culturally adapted hypertension education (CAHE) to improve blood pressure control and treatment adherence in patients of African origin with uncontrolled hypertension: cluster-randomized trial. *PLoS One*. 2014;9(3):e90103 doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0090103](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0090103) ; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC3943841
6. Horne R, Chapman SC, Parham R, Freemantle N, Forbes A, Cooper V. Understanding patients' adherence-related beliefs about medicines prescribed for long-term conditions: a meta-analytic review of the Necessity-Concerns Framework. *PLoS One*. 2013;8(12):e80633 doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0080633](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0080633) ; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC3846635.
 7. Aziz AM, Ibrahim MI. Medication noncompliance – a thriving problem. *Med J Malaysia*. 1999;54(2):192–199
 8. Turki AK, Sulaiman SAS. Elevated blood pressure among patients with hypertension in general hospital of Penang, Malaysia: does adherence matter? *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2010;2(1):24–32.
 9. Rizzo JA, Simons WR. Variations in compliance among hypertensive patients by drug class: implications for health care costs. *Clin Ther*. 1997;19(6):1446–1457
 10. Frances E, Nelson Marilyn K, Hart Robert F, Hart. Application of Control Chart Statistics to Blood Pressure Measurement Variability in the Primary Care Setting. *Am. J. Nurs*. January 1994 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-7599.1994.tb00889.x>
 11. Ramli, Azuana, Nur Sufiza Ahmad, and Thomas Paraidathathu. “Medication Adherence among Hypertensive Patients of Primary Health Clinics in Malaysia.” *Patient preference and adherence* 6 (2012): 613–622. *PMC*. Web. 4 May 2018.